

Multi-Parameter Machine Learning Enhanced Wi-Fi Handover in Dynamic Trajectory Simulations

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Abstract—There is a pressing need to enhance the connectivity between Wi-Fi stations and access points in scenarios where unmanned ground robots move in a dynamic environment, e.g., in manufacturing. In that context, optimizing handover management to minimize service disruptions and ensure seamless connectivity remains a topic with many unresolved challenges. Therefore, we propose a novel Multi-Parameter Machine Learning-based horizontal handover decision algorithm that leverages one among two proposed methodologies, whose results are compared. The first one combines a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network (NN) with a decision rule to predict key performance indicators, which are then used to determine the optimal connection strategy in the given environmental conditions. The decision rule offers simplicity and rapid execution, ideal for scenarios where immediate responses are required. The second one integrates the LSTM with a Classification NN to improve movement accuracy and adaptability in dynamically changing environments. The proposed methodologies, combined with leveraging multiple system parameters, enhance predictive capability, optimize handover timing, and reduce their frequency. Our findings demonstrate that our approach substantially outperforms the traditional handovers based on a single parameter, e.g., distance, especially in realistic curvilinear trajectories.

Index Terms—ML, Wi-Fi, Handover, Long-Short-Term Memory Neural Networks, Classification Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

As digitization of industrial manufacturing advances since a long time with each new generation of connectivity technology [1], [2], one of the main issues that still remains inadequately addressed is seamless handover in dynamically changing technological settings [3]. Indeed, enhanced handover management strategies are sought, especially in environments like harbours, industrial manufacturing sites, and smart cities, where an increasing number of unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) are being deployed [4].

In networks compliant with IEEE 802.11 standards, commonly known as Wi-Fi, the handover challenge can be simplified to establishing a reliable and continuous connection between Wi-Fi stations (STAs) and access points (APs), even when the link between the latter and the former has to be

This study was carried out within the PNRR research activities of the consortium iNEST (Interconnected North-Est Innovation Ecosystem) funded by the EU Next-GenerationEU (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) – Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – D.D. 1058 23/06/2022, ECS_00000043), and also partially funded by the EC Horizon Europe SNS JU PREDICT-6G (GA 101095890) and MULTIX (GA 101192521) Projects.

re-established due to any reason [5]. This is particularly crucial when STAs move rapidly and in complex trajectories within the coverage area of multiple APs, as frequent and unnecessary switches can degrade network performance. Each handover involves time-consuming processes such as scanning, authentication, and association, which may be less efficient than maintaining the current connection if another switch is likely to occur shortly thereafter [6].

In industrial environments, most handover optimization strategies are based on a single metric, e.g., Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) or distance between APs and STA. However, using a single metric to optimize processes is sub-optimal, especially in complex mobility environments, where wireless communication is influenced by other metrics, e.g., interference, network load, latency, throughput across multiple links, Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR), and packet delivery ratio (PDR), i.e., the ratio of packets received to packets sent [7].

To more effectively capture the complex state of wireless connections and avoid unnecessary handovers, we leverage Machine Learning (ML) techniques and introduce a novel Multi-Parameter ML (MPML)-based horizontal handover decision algorithm. MPML employs a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Network (NN), to forecast Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), e.g., latency, SNR, and RSSI for each AP, for future time intervals, enabling proactive insight into the anticipated values. The LSTM NN uses the distance of the STAs from each AP, their coordinates (x, y) , speed, and direction of movement to forecast predictive metrics. These predictions serve as inputs to two methodologies, i.e., either a decision rule or a Classification NN, whose results are compared to decide the optimal AP to connect.

Our solution outperforms other traditional single-parameter-based methods by offering a more comprehensive and adaptive framework for horizontal handover management. By integrating multiple parameters, MPML provides a robust mechanism for optimizing connectivity in dynamic and complex environments commonly found in manufacturing.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 overviews the state of the art in handover optimization. Section 3 describes MPML. Section 4 presents the experimental setup and analyzes the results obtained comparing our approach against the chosen baseline. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the paper and highlights future work.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART ANALYSIS

ML is increasingly impactful in various vertical sectors. In manufacturing, ML optimizes production processes by predicting equipment failures and scheduling maintenance, thereby reducing downtime. In logistics, ML improves supply chain management by forecasting demand and optimizing routes, ensuring timely delivery and resource allocation. The financial sector benefits from predictive analytics of ML for risk assessment and fraud detection, improving security and decision-making. In healthcare, ML improves disease diagnosis and treatment personalization, enhancing patient outcomes [8].

Due to their capabilities, also NNs are getting more and more relevant across different domains. In smart cities, NNs significantly help in traffic management, energy distribution, and public safety [4]. In industrial automation, NNs can greatly improve the performance of machine vision applications, for instance in better navigating UGVs in non-linear computational landscapes [9]. Particularly in the field of communication NNs have been proved to provide significant benefits. In the security domain, as in [10], LSTM NN are deployed together with federated learning methods to optimize privacy-preserving handovers. [11] proposes a framework that leverages the Gittins index to determine the optimal stopping point in fractional Markovian multi-objective selection procedures, commonly used in handover decisions. [12] offers another theoretical approach, comparing a novel convolutional NN structure with LSTM structures, using measured Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) values to decide whether to perform a handover. [13] employs a multi-step time-series prediction approach to tackle the handover prediction problem, proposing a solution using the random forest supervised learning algorithm, which appears to reduce unnecessary handovers by 60% compared to the RSS method. In [14], an anticipation-based handover solution using a Kalman filter to predict short-term RSSI changes is introduced, allowing proactive scanning and handover execution when better APs are available. However, this approach is limited by its reliance on RSSI alone. [15] focuses only on maximizing throughput considering the AP load and the available bandwidth, neglecting other important metrics. Similarly in [16] the handover decision is based only on the distance between the STA and the APs, even if authors propose an interesting real set-up using wireless Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) and ML to determine the optimal handover timing and location in a 2-dimensional (2D) environment. [17] tackles optimization of cellular networks supporting Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), focusing on the reduction of the number of handovers leveraging reinforcement learning techniques.

Several works enhance Wi-Fi features to improve operations in industrial environments. [18] proposes a new architectural split of Wi-Fi functionalities based on an enhanced software-defined wireless architecture, enabling uninterrupted communication during handovers, and faster failover management of UGVs operating in a factory. Also [19] focuses on a UGV use case taking advantage of the redundancy capabilities of

the TSN standard (IEEE 802.11CB) to reduce outages and delays during roaming. [20] uses the Generalized Precision Time Protocol (gPTP) standard (IEEE 802.1AS) to investigate the impact of clock synchronization errors and latency on trajectory tracking. [21] exploits Digital Twins (DTs) for moving STAs in Wi-Fi 7 networks supporting Multi-Link Operation (MLO) (IEEE 802.11be) to achieve seamless roaming between APs. [22] proposes an LSTM-based link-quality estimation model that focuses only on predicting the RSRP metric. Finally, Wi-Fi is increasingly used in synergy with other wireless technologies, e.g., LoRA, to enable reliable and efficient communication over long distances, making this approach particularly relevant in sensor networks and smart cities [23]. [24] proposes a multi-criteria mechanism but for vertical handovers in SDN-based mixed cellular/Wi-Fi networks, leveraging entropy to calculate the weights for the handover decision criterion and obtaining interesting results. A comprehensive overview of wireless aspects in smart manufacturing, open challenges, and the relationship between cellular and Wi-Fi networks can be found in [25].

The aforementioned papers rely on a single metric, neglecting several other KPIs that we instead consider, including latency, SNR, and RSSI, which significantly affect the quality and reliability of wireless connections. For example, considering only the distance between the STA and the APs can lead to a wrong decision, since signal quality, congestion of the APs, and interference from other signals can affect the connection quality. Moreover, not only handover optimization techniques in cellular networks by far outnumber comparable works in Wi-Fi networks, but also vertical handovers are studied more extensively than horizontal ones. This work helps address these imbalances. Finally, it should be mentioned that [20] provides the foundation for this work and that [26] focuses on a similar setup to this paper, but using the MLO capabilities of Wi-Fi 7 and considering the interference from two additional fixed STAs. Instead this work presents a simpler setup but compares the effectiveness of two different methods applied after the LSTM NN in the MPML algorithm flow.

Hence MPML distinguishes itself from other approaches and offers advantages that improve the quality of wireless connections, as described in the next section.

III. THE MPML ALGORITHM

The MPML algorithm presents a novel two-step NN architecture for the handover trigger and the prediction of the best target AP. It employs two distinct methodologies: (i) an LSTM network paired with a decision rule and (ii) an LSTM network followed by a classification NN. The first approach ensures rapid execution, making it ideal for situations requiring immediate responses. In contrast, the second approach improves adaptability in dynamically evolving environments. Fig. 1 schematically shows the MPML flow, whereas Alg. 1 details its pseudocode.

Firstly, MPML enables a comprehensive metric analysis by evaluating multiple factors, offering a more complete view of network conditions. This is complemented by higher

prediction accuracy thanks to the LSTM, which improves the reliability of handover decisions by anticipating future network states. Based on this prediction capability, MPML supports proactive and more informed decision-making by allowing adjustments based on expected future conditions. This reduces the probability of unnecessary handovers and minimizes interruptions, ensuring smoother transitions between APs. Furthermore, adaptability to dynamic environments is a key feature, as the algorithm incorporates multiple KPIs. This allows optimal connectivity to be maintained even in complex and dynamic scenarios as those found in manufacturing.

Fig. 1: MPML algorithm procedure. Black arrows: sequential flow of data through the processing pipeline. Blue arrows: coordination and distribution of tasks from the task queue to the relevant components. Red arrows: execution and management of tasks by the task management system

Our algorithm employs a task queue system to support concurrent task execution using a thread-safe queue to manage tasks systematically in a multi-threaded scenario. This includes data processing via the LSTM model and network flow adjustments based on the output of the decision rule or of the Classification NN. Monitoring and logging tasks are integral to tracking system performance and recording relevant data for analysis. Hence, task management is overseen by a dedicated thread that continuously monitors the task queue, ensuring controlled task execution, preventing race conditions, and maintaining thread safety. Finally, the task enqueueing mechanism locks the queue, adds tasks, and alerts the processing thread, facilitating prompt task handling and preserving system responsiveness.

To assess the effectiveness of our method in Wi-Fi 7 networks, KPIs obtained by MPML, e.g., latency, PDR, and the number of handovers between APs, are compared against the ones obtained by the distance-based method.

A. Development and Training of the LSTM model

Data collection is carried out through a series of simulations in which the STA moves in a 2D space, following linear and

Algorithm 1 MPML algorithm

```

1: Start Task Processing:
2: while not stopped do
3:   Wait for tasks or stop signal
4:   if stop signal and no tasks then break
5:   end if
6:   Execute task from queue
7: end while
8: Add Task:
9: Add task to queue and notify
10: Manage Network Flows:
11: if final output is different from previous final output then
12:   Configure and start network flows
13:   Stop previous running applications
14: end if
15: Process Incoming Data:
16: while not stopped do
17:   Wait for data or stop signal
18:   Normalize and predict future states
19:   Apply Classification NN and update final output
20:   Add task if final output is different from previous final
   output
21: end while
22: Collect Mobility Data:
23: Collect the last 10 time instances data:  $(x, y)$  STA posi-
   tion,  $(v_x, v_y)$  velocities
24: Notify data queue
25: Schedule Data Collection:
26: Schedule data collection every 10 ms
27: Check and add tasks if needed
  
```

curvilinear trajectories and changing its velocity and initial position to guarantee the development of a robust NN model. The starting position of the STA and its velocity are generated randomly, but ensuring the STA moves in an area of 2500 m². In detail, the most prevalent curvilinear movements in manufacturing are considered, including circular, arc, elliptical, and spiral paths. To ensure comprehensive data acquisition for both APs, each simulation is executed twice using the distance-based approach: first, with the STA connecting to the nearest AP, then with the STA connecting to the farthest AP.

To effectively implement this approach, the system collects data from the most recent 10 time instants, each of which occurs every 10 ms. Specifically, the controller captures the position (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) and the velocity (v_x, v_y) of the STA. With the known positions of the APs, the controller preprocesses these data to structure them as input for the LSTM model. The preprocessing involves calculating the distances to each AP, as well as the speed and direction of the STA.

Hence, the 6 input features of the LSTM model include the coordinates of the STA (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) , its speed calculated as $v = \sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2}$, its direction of movement given by $\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{v_y}{v_x}\right)$, and the distances between the STA

and each AP, i.e., $d_{STA,AP1}$ and $d_{STA,AP2}$ computed as $\sqrt{(x_{STA} - x_{AP_i})^2 + (y_{STA} - y_{AP_i})^2}$ with $i \in 1, 2$.

The collected data are organized to provide a look-back of 10 time steps, with KPIs, i.e., lat_{AP1} , SNR_{AP1} , $RSSI_{AP1}$, lat_{AP2} , SNR_{AP2} , $RSSI_{AP2}$, computed as mean values at constant intervals of 10 ms. In particular, the latency is considered as the end-to-end (E2E) latency, from STA to AP; the RSSI, expressed in dBm, is computed using the free space path loss model that considers the transmitted power and the positions of the STA and the AP; the SNR is calculated as the difference between the received signal power and the thermal noise power density at room temperature.

The complete data set, obtained by concatenating the data sets from each simulation run, is normalized using `StandardScaler`, scaling each feature individually. It was organized to ensure that each simulation is processed in separate batches, preventing data mixing between different simulations and allowing the model to learn independently of each simulation. The data set is divided into training, validation, and test sets in a 60 : 20 : 20 ratio. Using the preprocessed inputs, the LSTM model predicts KPIs for each AP over a 300 ms prediction horizon. The selection of the look-back and prediction horizon values is guided by the trade-off between the accuracy and the response time of the model. Using 10 previous intervals and predicting the next 30 offers a more effective balance between real-time processing and accuracy in prediction.

The LSTM architecture consists of two layers, each with a hidden size of 128, which process the input sequences and generate hidden states through fully connected layers with Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions. The final output layer is responsible for predicting the KPIs. The model is trained using a masked mean square error (MSE) loss function to effectively handle missing or invalid data points.

The selection of the hyperparameter starts with values deemed reasonable on the basis of previous research in the domain. Such values are subsequently fine-tuned via an iterative process, guided by the performance metrics of the model, including prediction accuracy and loss function evaluation. This empirical approach facilitates the convergence to a local minimum, as validated by the test simulations performed.

Furthermore, this model was designed as a one-shot solution, meaning that it was trained only once on a Next Unit of Computing (NUC) equipped with an Intel 11th Gen Core processor, without the use of a GPU. It effectively handles the task without requiring retraining, provided that the data and environment remain consistent.

B. Handover Decision Rule

To ensure stable handover decisions, a mathematical framework is designed to identify the optimal AP utilizing the values predicted by the LSTM for the next 30 time steps:

$$s_i = \left\{ \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)}, \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)}, \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right) \right\}_{t=1}^T$$

where $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ represents discrete time steps within the considered time window, so that each s_i captures the SNR, RSSI and latency values observed for AP i at time step t .

For each set of latency, SNR, and RSSI values corresponding to each AP, a score is calculated as in Eq. 1:

$$\mathcal{S}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)} + \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)} - \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right) \quad (1)$$

The optimal AP at each time is found by selecting the highest score, as shown in Eq. 2.

$$\text{BestAP}^{(t)} = \arg \max_i \mathcal{S}_i \quad (2)$$

Hence, the selected AP is the one most frequently identified as optimal over the predicted time steps. This approach ensures robust and stable handover decisions, optimizing network performance through KPI analysis.

C. Development and Training of the Classification NN

To support intelligent AP selection using predicted KPIs in complex scenarios and to extend the applicability of the algorithm in future works involving networks with multiple APs and STAs, a Classification NN is employed to enhance overall network performance. This classification model operates on the sequence of KPIs, output features of the LSTM model, for both APs with the goal of classifying the data into one of two classes, corresponding to AP1 or AP2, thus determining the optimal AP to connect with the STA.

The dataset used to train the Classification NN comprises the concatenated KPIs values for each AP, which were previously used as target features for the LSTM model, i.e., lat_{AP1} , SNR_{AP1} , $RSSI_{AP1}$, lat_{AP2} , SNR_{AP2} , and $RSSI_{AP2}$.

Hence, the input to the Classification NN consists of temporal sequences of the previously predicted 6 features. Each sequence comprises 30 consecutive time steps, according to the prediction horizon of the LSTM model. Each input feature is individually standardized using the `StandardScaler`, ensuring uniform scaling throughout the dataset. This approach aligns with the normalization applied during the LSTM training, thereby eliminating the need to re-normalize the predicted KPIs before feeding them into the Classification NN.

Classification labels are derived based on a score computed for each AP within a sequence window, as already shown in Eq. 1. Hence, the classification label $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is assigned based on the AP with the highest score \mathcal{S}_i , enabling the model to learn to choose the AP with the highest expected performance over the given time window:

$$y = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mathcal{S}_1 > \mathcal{S}_2 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The data set is then partitioned into training, validation and test sets in a ratio 60 : 20 : 20.

The architecture of the Classification NN comprises 3 fully connected layers. ReLU activations are used between layers and the dropout is applied after each hidden layer

for regularization. The model is optimized using the Adam optimizer and the cross-entropy loss is used as the objective function. As done for the LSTM model, the hyper-parameter values were established in an empirical manner.

IV. RESULTS

The MPML algorithm is implemented and validated within the ns3 network simulator, modeling the functional parameters and communication behaviors in a manufacturing environment. Our simulated network comprises one STA, which interacts with a pair of stationary APs, i.e., AP1 and AP2, a centralized server, and a remote control unit responsible for real-time network optimization, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: System view as implemented in the ns3 simulator

In this configuration, the STA, which can be seen as a UGV operating in a factory, acts as a data source, continuously transmitting frames to the AP to which it is connected, using Wi-Fi 7. As the STA moves through the environment, it crosses the coverage area of both APs, triggering the handover process. For example, as illustrated, when the STA, initially connected to AP1, moves into the overlapping coverage area, it disconnects from AP1 and begins communication with AP2. Consequently, when the STA exits the overlapping area, it remains connected to AP2. The frames received by the APs are then sent to the server, which acts only as receiver, via Ethernet connections. Hence, the traffic is unidirectional, from the STA to the server. The STA connects only to one AP at the time, and the choice to which AP the STA has to connect to is provided by the off-board controller, which is responsible for evaluating handovers and determining the optimal AP for the STA through the proposed optimized approach.

Given such an architecture, the network configuration parameters include:

- the transmission power, set to 17 dBm for the STA and to 20 dBm for the APs;
- two transmit and receive antennas for each node;

- the duration of the maximum transmission opportunity (txop) for APs and STA, set to 5600 ms;
- the interval between consecutive beacon transmissions, required to maintain network synchronization and announcing to STA the AP presence and capabilities, which is equal to 102.4 ms;
- the network load, set to 10 Mbps.

Mobility is introduced only through the STA, which follows linear or curvilinear trajectories, while AP1 and AP2 remain fixed at coordinates (15, 15) and (15, 35), respectively, in a 2D space free from obstacles and disturbances. Hence, integrating our model into the ns3 simulator, together with multithreading for data processing and network flow management, supports accurate and responsive modeling of real-time decision-making processes, neglecting other aspects, e.g., interferences, that will be taken care of in future works.

To validate the effectiveness of the trained LSTM model, its prediction accuracy and generalization capability are thoroughly evaluated. After 78 epochs, the training and validation losses converge to 0.0733 and 0.0790, respectively, underscoring the effectiveness of the model training process and marking the stage at which the model reliably generalizes to unseen data. Further insights into the ability of the model to predict KPIs are presented, for both linear and curvilinear trajectories, in Fig. 3. The plots illustrate in orange the measured KPIs obtained using the distance-based approach, while the LSTM predictions of such KPIs are depicted in blue. A careful analysis of the figure reveals a minor discrepancy in some KPI values, which highlights an opportunity for refinement in future research. In fact, by integrating real-world parameters into the model, these discrepancies can be further minimized, enhancing the accuracy of the KPI predictions.

Instead, after 51 epochs, the training and validation losses of the Classification NN converge to 0.00163 and 0.00179, respectively. The confusion matrix underscores the precision of the model, achieving an accuracy of 99.93% when comparing the predicted labels to the ground truth, which was established using a distance-based method.

To assess the MPML performance, a comparative analysis focusing on average latency throughout the simulations is conducted. The MPML algorithm is compared with a baseline method in which handover decisions are based solely on distance. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, 100 different test simulations are performed for both methodologies. In these simulations, the STA starts moving from various initial positions within the environment and moves with different velocities, generating linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Table I and Table II provide a comparative analysis of average performance metrics between two handover approaches: the MPML algorithm, using the Classification NN (Table I) or the decision rule (Table II), against the conventional distance-based method. The analysis distinguishes between linear and curvilinear trajectories. The performance metrics evaluated include average latency, latency standard deviation, average number of handovers (switches), and PDR.

Fig. 3: Predicted KPIs provided by the LSTM model (in blue) against the measured data provided by the distance-based approach (in orange). If no values are represented, the AP was not used at that specific timestamp

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPML Handover Classification NN	0.50	0.18	97.43	1
Distance-based Handover	0.50	0.18	97.57	1

(a) Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPML Handover Classification NN	1.46	2.75	93.10	1.19
Distance-based Handover	6.32	12.89	94.27	2.44

(b) Curvilinear trajectories

TABLE I: MPML with Classification NN vs distance-based method, evaluating average latency, latency standard deviation, PDR and number of occurred handovers for linear and curvilinear trajectories.

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPML Handover Decision Rule	0.53	0.20	96.95	1
Distance-based Handover	0.53	0.20	97.09	1

(a) Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPML Handover Decision Rule	1.63	2.92	93.61	1.09
Distance-based Handover	5.68	12.99	94.16	2.29

(b) Curvilinear trajectories

TABLE II: MPML with decision rule vs distance-based method, evaluating average latency, latency standard deviation, PDR and number of occurred handovers for linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Table Ia, related to the linear trajectory scenario, shows that MPML yields results very similar to the distance-based method. The average E2E latency values differ by as little as $0.6 \mu s$, the average PDR values by 0.14% , the average switch number is the same. Even though MPML obtains limited gains in this scenario, it is noteworthy that it still outperforms the distance-based method in 60% of the simulation runs.

Table Ib, related to the curvilinear trajectory scenario, shows that the MPML algorithm reduces latency by $4.86 ms$, a notable improvement of 76.90% against the distance-based method. This reduction aligns with the decrease in the average number of handovers, indicating that MPML effectively avoids unnecessary switches between APs when the STA moves rapidly across the coverage area. Furthermore, it should be noted that the LSTM model achieves a PDR of 93.1% , a bit lower than the PDR of the distance-based method (94.27%). This suggests that the MPML algorithm significantly reduces latency and handovers. Overall, taking into account only

curvilinear trajectories, the MPML algorithm outperforms the distance-based method in 73.33% of the simulation runs.

Table IIa shows similar results in terms of latency and number of switches. However, the MPML algorithm demonstrates a slightly lower PDR compared to the distance-based approach and outperforms it in 60% of the simulation runs.

Table IIb shows significant performance improvements delivered by the MPML algorithm, including a $4.05 ms$ decrease in average E2E latency and fewer handovers. Despite this, the MPML algorithm has a slightly lower PDR compared to the distance-based approach. The MPML algorithm outperforms the distance-based method in 66.66% of the simulation trials.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we introduce an innovative and optimized approach for managing Wi-Fi horizontal handovers. Our main objective is to demonstrate the validity and effectiveness of the proposed MPML algorithm in improving network perfor-

mance, neglecting at this stage other factors like interference or complexity of the set-up. The experimental results obtained by MPML show significant improvements in reducing both the E2E latency and the average number of handover transitions, compared to traditional distance-based baselines. This progress is particularly evident when the STA moves quickly through the overlapped coverage areas of two APs. A key feature of our approach is the decision-making process for handover, which is based on multiple parameters: latency, SNR and RSSI. Taking these different metrics into account, the MPML algorithm offers a more comprehensive and adaptive solution, which makes it particularly promising for complex network environments involving multiple STAs and APs. Our multi-parameter strategy contrasts with traditional approaches that rely on a single metric, providing a more nuanced and effective handover decision-making process. Our results highlight a key point: maintaining a stable connection with a single AP is more efficient than performing frequent, close handover. This efficiency comes from the inherent delays associated with the handover process, which involves scanning, association, and authentication. These steps introduce latency and temporarily interrupt communication between the STA and the AP, negatively impacting overall network performance. By minimizing unnecessary handovers and leveraging multiple metrics for decision making, our approach not only improves communication stability, but also optimizes resource utilization, ensuring a smoother and more responsive user experience. This highlights the potential of the MPML algorithm to transform Wi-Fi handover strategies, paving the way for more robust and efficient wireless networks.

In conclusion, the proposed methodology offers a promising solution to improve Wi-Fi horizontal handover efficiency, particularly in dynamic environments where rapid STA movements are frequent. This work lays the foundation for future research and development of adaptive handover strategies with the potential to have a significant impact on real-world applications in wireless communication, especially in industrial manufacturing environments.

Future works will focus on more realistic cases to enhance the applicability of MPML. Numerous STAs and APs will be deployed so that the LSTM can be challenged in diverse network conditions and the Classification NN can be utilized to optimize a more complex network than the STA-APs connection.

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